

“Chance Denkmal” – An innovative sales practice for listed buildings

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As a part of the RAG Immobilien GmbH, the real estate branch of the RAG group, the Montan-Grundstücksgesellschaft mbH (MGG), owns and administers 115 industrial heritage buildings in the Ruhr and Saar regions of Germany. Many of these buildings are listed monuments with a considerable relevance for both the local and regional identity and, moreover, displaying exceptional architectural and urban design quality. The collieries, coking plants and former headquarters with their winding towers, pithead baths, gatehouses and halls in which the miners received their weekly pay bear witness to the industrial past of the communities. Having lost the purposes they were originally designed for, many of these buildings are currently not used and thus wait for developers and investors with new ideas to put them back into use. With “Chance Denkmal”, MGG designed and implemented a new sales practice to quicker let entrepreneurs put their ideas into practice in industrial heritage buildings: 22 objects – both individual buildings and ensembles – had been selected to be assigned according to two tender and one competition procedures.

- o The first tender procedure offered smaller scale buildings, linked to explicit use options, to real estate end users.
- o The second tender procedure was addressed to real estate professionals. It dealt with larger buildings respectively complex ensembles which are suitable for different use options and/or combinations among these.
- o The third procedure, the “Chance Denkmal Award”, was looking for the most innovative ideas and future use concepts for exceptional heritage buildings. These buildings were not sold to the highest bid, but awarded to the best concept in order to support its implementation.

Started in June 2006, "Chance Denkmal" was completed in December 2006. To promote the project, MGG wrote to 6.000 developers, estate agents and architects and informed the public by means of press conferences, publications and advertisements. All 22 objects were presented to the interested parties during a kick-off event and several site visits. The interested parties were given four months of time to put together their use concepts and bids and to organise their finance. The result of "Chance Denkmal" is worth looking at:

- o In the context of the tender procedures, seven buildings could be sold by today. Moreover, additional 10 buildings are currently subject of negotiations.
- o Within the competition procedure, the Zunft AG was awarded the first prize for its both conceptionally and economically convincing vision to develop the 1959 built so-called "Kammgebäude" of the former coking plant Zollverein in Essen-Katernberg into the Zunft[viertel] Zollverein, a communicative quarter incorporating manufactures, studios, regional handcrafts, retailing and gastronomy. The Zunft[viertel] is themed around topics such as wood, textile, design, metal, jewellery, leather, porcelain and glass, providing quality products for daily use. The "hall of manufactures" is joined by smaller studios ideal for tailor-made clothing, shoemakers, design products and cabinet makers. The concept is completed by a market for quality food and wellness and healthcare services. The concept covers 11.000 sqm of floorspace with the architectural design being elaborated by Koschany + Zimmer KZA from Essen.

Evaluation and future prospects

Selling one third of those objects formerly tagged "not marketable", Chance Denkmal proved to be a successful sales practice for listed buildings. With 10 more buildings still under negotiation, more sales are likely to come in the near future.

Because of this success, MGG is working on the continuation of "Chance Denkmal". Here, the time frame for the objects' availability and their potential use options play a major role. To further increase the practice's success, the scale and the regional setting of priorities together with the required scope of documents to be handed in are currently assessed.